

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 35

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each psalm offers. Each psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

It shall ^bexult in His salvation.
¹⁰ All my ^abones will say, "LORD,
^bwho is like You,
Who delivers the afflicted from
him ^awho is too strong for him,
And ^a"the afflicted and the needy
from him who robs him?"
¹¹ ^a"Malicious witnesses rise up;
They ask me of things that I do
not know.
¹² They ^a"repay me evil for good,
To the bereavement of my soul.
¹³ But as for me, ^a"when they were
sick, my ^bclothing was sackcloth;
I ^a"humbled my soul with fasting,
And my ^a"prayer kept returning to
my bosom.
¹⁴ I went about as though it were my
friend or brother;
I ^a"bowed down ¹mourning, as one
who sorrows for a mother.
¹⁵ But ^a"at my ¹stumbling they
rejoiced and gathered themselves
together;
The ^{2b}smiters whom I did not
know gathered together against me,
They ³slandered me without
ceasing.
¹⁶ Like godless jesters at a feast,
They ^a"gnashed at me with their
teeth.
Psa. 35:17 Lord, ^a"how long will You
look on?
Rescue my soul ^bfrom their
ravages,
My ^aonly *life* from the lions.
¹⁸ I will ^a"give You thanks in the great
congregation;
I will ^bpraise You among a mighty
throng.

מִתְזַקֵּם מִמֵּנִי וְעַנִּי וְאֶבְיוֹן
מִגִּזְלוֹ : ¹¹ יִקְוּמוּן עֵדֵי חַמָּס
אֲשֶׁר לֹא-יָדְעוּתִי יִשְׁאַלּוּנִי :
¹² יִשְׁלֹמוּנִי רָעָה תַּחַת טוֹבָה
שְׂכֹוֹל לְנַפְשִׁי : ¹³ וְאֲנִי |
בַּחֲלוֹתָם לְבוֹשֵׁי שֹׁק עֵינֵי תִי
בְצוּם נַפְשִׁי וְתַפְלֵתִי עַל-
חִיקֵי תְּשׁוּב : ¹⁴ כִּרְע-כְּאֶח
לִי הִתְהַלַּכְתִּי כְּאֶבֶל-אֵם
קִדְר שְׁחוֹתִי : ¹⁵ וּבְצִלְעֵי
שְׂמֹחוֹ וְנֶאֱסָפוּ נֶאֱסָפוּ עָלַי
גִּבִּים וְלֹא יָדְעוּתִי קִרְעוּ
וְלֹא-דָמוּ : ¹⁶ בַּחֲנֹפִי לְעֵגִי
מְעוֹג חָרַק עָלַי שְׁנֵימוֹ : ¹⁷
אֲדַנִּי כַּמָּה תִּרְאֶה הַשִּׁיבָה
נַפְשִׁי מִשְׂאֵיהֶם מִכַּפְיָרִים
יַחֲדָתִי : ¹⁸ אֲוֹדֶךָ בְּקִתְּל רַב
בְּעַם עֲצוּם אֶתְהַלֵּךְ : ¹⁹ אֶל-
יִשְׂמְחוּ-לִי אֵיבֵי שֹׁקֶר שְׂנְאֵי
חַנָּם יִקְרְצוּ-עֵינַי : ²⁰ כִּי לֹא
שָׁלוֹם יִדְבְּרוּ וְעַל רַגְעֵי-

¹⁹ ^aDo not let those who are wrongfully ^bmy enemies rejoice over me; Nor let those ^cwho hate me without cause ^{1d}wink maliciously.

²⁰ For they do not speak peace, But they devise ^adeceitful words against those who are quiet in the land.

²¹ They ^aopened their mouth wide against me;

They said, "^bAha, aha, our eyes have seen it!"

Psa. 35:22 ^aYou have seen it, O LORD, ^bdo not keep silent;

O Lord, ^cdo not be far from me.

²³ ^aStir up Yourself, and awake to my right

And to my cause, my God and my Lord.

²⁴ ^aJudge me, O LORD my God, according to Your righteousness,

And ^bdo not let them rejoice over me.

²⁵ Do not let them say in their heart, "^aAha, our desire!"

Do not let them say, "We have ^bswallowed him up!"

²⁶ Let ^athose be ashamed and humiliated altogether who rejoice at my distress;

Let those be ^bclothed with shame and dishonor who ^cmagnify themselves over me.

Psa. 35:27 Let them ^ashout for joy and rejoice, who favor ^bmy vindication;

And ^clet them say continually, "The LORD be magnified,

Who ^ddelights in the prosperity of His servant."

אָרֶץ דְּבַרֵי מְרֻמֹּת יִחְשְׁבוּן :
וַיִּרְחִיבוּ עָלַי פִּיֵּיהֶם אָמְרוּ :

הָאֵת וְהָאֵת רָאִתָּה עֵינֵינוּ :
רָאִיתָה יְהוָה אֶל-תְּחַרֵּשׁ

אֶדְנִי אֶל-תִּרְחַק מִמֶּנִּי :
הָעִירָה וְהִקְיָצָה לְמִשְׁפָּטֵי

אֱלֹהֵי וְאֶדְנִי לְרִיבִי :
שָׁפְטֵנִי כְצַדִּיק וְהוֹדָה אֱלֹהֵי

וְאֶל-יִשְׁמְחוּ-לִי :
יֹאמְרוּ בְלִבָּם הָאֵת נִפְשָׁנוּ

אֶל-יֹאמְרוּ בְּלִעְנוֹהוּ :
וְיִחְפְּרוּ אֶת-יְחִדּוֹ שְׁמִתִּי

רָעִתִי יִלְבְּשוּ-בִשְׂת וְכִלְמָה
הַמְגִדִילִים עָלַי :
וְיִשְׁמְחוּ חֲפִצֵי צַדִּיק וְיֹאמְרוּ

תְּמִיד יִגְדַּל יְהוָה הֶחָפֵץ
שְׁלוֹם עַבְדּוֹ :
תְּהַנֶּה צַדִּיק כָּל-הַיּוֹם

תְּהַלֵּלֵהוּ :

<p>²⁸ And ^amy tongue shall declare Your righteousness <i>And</i> Your praise all day long.</p>	
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References

<p>Psalm 35:1 ^aPs 18:43; Is 49:25 ^bPs 56:2</p> <p>Psalm 35:2 ¹i.e. small shield ^aPs 91:4 ^bPs 44:26</p> <p>Psalm 35:3 ¹Or <i>close up the path against those</i> ^aPs 62:2</p> <p>Psalm 35:4 ¹Or <i>soul</i> ^aPs 70:2 ^bPs 40:14; 129:5</p> <p>Psalm 35:5 ^aJob 21:18; Ps 83:13; Is 29:5</p> <p>Psalm 35:6 ^aPs 73:18; Jer 23:12</p> <p>Psalm 35:7 ¹<i>Pit</i> has been transposed from line above ^aPs 69:4; 109:3; 140:5 ^bPs 9:15</p> <p>Psalm 35:8 ^aPs 55:23; Is 47:11; 1 Thess 5:3 ^bPs 9:15 ^cPs 73:18</p> <p>Psalm 35:9 ^aIs 61:10 ^bPs 9:14; 13:5; Luke 1:47</p>	<p>Psalm 35:10 ^aPs 51:8 ^bEx 15:11; Ps 86:8; Mic 7:18 ^cPs 18:17 ^dPs 37:14; 109:16</p> <p>Psalm 35:11 ^aPs 27:12</p> <p>Psalm 35:12 ^aPs 38:20; 109:5; Jer 18:20; John 10:32</p> <p>Psalm 35:13 ^aJob 30:25 ^bPs 69:11 ^cPs 69:10 ^dMatt 10:13; Luke 10:6</p> <p>Psalm 35:14 ¹Or <i>dressed in black</i> ^aPs 38:6</p> <p>Psalm 35:15 ¹Or <i>limping</i> ²Or <i>smitten ones</i> ³Lit <i>tore</i> ^aObad 12 ^bJob 30:1, 8, 12 ^cPs 7:2</p> <p>Psalm 35:16 ^aJob 16:9; Ps 37:12; Lam 2:16</p> <p>Psalm 35:17 ^aPs 13:1; Hab 1:13 ^bPs 35:7 ^cPs 22:20, 21</p>
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Psalm 35:18

^aPs 22:22

^bPs 22:25

Psalm 35:19

¹Or *wink the eye*

^aPs 13:4; 30:1; 38:16

^bPs 38:19; 69:4

^cJohn 15:25

^dProv 6:13; 10:10

Psalm 35:20

^aPs 55:21; Jer 9:8; Mic 6:12

Psalm 35:21

^aJob 16:10; Ps 22:13

^bPs 40:15; 70:3

Psalm 35:22

^aEx 3:7; Ps 10:14

^bPs 28:1

^cPs 10:1; 22:11; 38:21; 71:12

Psalm 35:23

^aPs 7:6; 44:23; 59:4; 80:2

Psalm 35:24

^aPs 9:4; 26:1; 43:1

^bPs 35:19

Psalm 35:25

^aPs 35:21

^bPs 56:1; 124:3; Prov 1:12; Lam 2:16

Psalm 35:26

^aPs 40:14

^bPs 109:29

^cJob 19:5; Ps 38:16

Psalm 35:27

^aPs 32:11

^bPs 9:4

^cPs 40:16; 70:4

^dPs 147:11; 149:4

Psalm 35:28

^aPs 51:14; 71:15, 24

Targum

Psa. 35:1 Of David. Contend, O LORD, with those who contend against me; make war against those who war against me. ² Take up a shield and buckler, and arise as my help. ³ And draw the spear and fasten the scabbard; and be prepared to meet those who pursue me; say to my soul, "I am your redeemer." ⁴ Let those who seek my life be ashamed and embarrassed; let those who plot my ruin shrink back and be subdued. ⁵ Let them be like chaff before the storm-wind, with the angel of the LORD repelling [them]. ⁶ May their paths be dark and murky, with the angel of the LORD pursuing them. ⁷ For without cause they have spread before me a pit; their net they have hidden for my soul without cause. ⁸ May a sudden calamity, unsuspected, overtake him; and may his net that he spread catch him; let him suddenly fall in it. ⁹ But my soul will rejoice in the word of the LORD; it will be glad in his redemption. ¹⁰ All my limbs will keep saying, "O LORD, who is like you?" – who saves the poor from the one stronger than he, and the poor and wretched from his oppressor. ¹¹ Rapacious witnesses stand up; those whom I have not known question me. ¹² They repay me evil for good, seeking to bereave my soul. ¹³ But I, in the time of their illness, wore sackcloth; I afflicted my soul with fasting; but my prayer will return to my bosom. ¹⁴ As if for my friend or brother, I went about like a mourner; like one who mourns for his mother, I was bowed down in gloom. ¹⁵ But when I was stricken, they rejoiced and even gathered together against me; the wicked, who belittle me with their words, and I knew it not, as if they cut my skin without drawing blood. ¹⁶ With smooth words and haughtiness and mockery, they grind their teeth against me. ¹⁷ O LORD, how long will you watch? Deliver my soul from their calamities, my body from the lion's whelps. ¹⁸ I will give thanks in your presence in the great assembly; among a mighty people I will praise you. ¹⁹ Let not my enemies rejoice over me [with] a lie – those who hate me without cause, winking with their eyes. ²⁰ For they do not speak peace; and against the righteous of the earth who have rest in this world they plot devious things. ²¹ And they have opened their mouth wide against me [and] said, "Joy! Joy! Our eye has seen it!" ²² You have seen, O LORD, do not be silent; O LORD, be not far from me. ²³ Wake and be alert to my cause, O my God; the LORD is the victor in my dispute. ²⁴ Judge me by your generosity, O LORD my God, and they will not rejoice over me. ²⁵ Let them not say in their heart, "Our soul is glad"; lest they say, "We have finished him." ²⁶ Let those who rejoice at my harm be ashamed and subdued together; let those who vaunt themselves over me be clothed with shame and disgrace. ²⁷ May those who seek my vindication be glad and rejoice and say always, "May the glory of the LORD be great, he who desires the peace of his servant." ²⁸ And my tongue will sing of your generosity, all the day of your praise.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses are in bold.

Introduction

This psalm is about a hopeful declaration of David's beliefs in the LORD expressed in Psalm 34. David makes another request from the LORD to redeem him from the menace of his many enemies.

Verse 1

רִיבָה (reeva) – means "to strive, contend." The usage of this word indicates that there were enemies whose opposition to David and Israel was a part of their character and fundamental outlook on life. The struggle David was in was one-sided. He did not reciprocate against his enemies' hostilities. Today some people are antisemitic for no reason other than that it is a part of their character. Many of these people have little to no contact with Semitic people, yet they strive to hurt and destroy the Semitic race. This psalm applies to these modern-day persons.

By David. Strive, O LORD, with those that contend against me; fight against them that fight against me because of who I am.

Verse 2

הִחַזַּק (hachazeaq) – means "be(come) strong, strengthen, prevail, harden, be courageous." In the context of this verse, this word refers to a shield that can repel missiles even if they are hurled from a great distance.

סִנָּא (sinna) – means "large shield." This word refers to a spiked shield used to ward off the direct, head-on attack.

Take hold of the shield and spiked shield and rise up to my help.

Verse 3

David is probably referring to a defensive weapon.

And draw out the spear and barrier against them who pursue me, saying to my soul that I am your salvation.

Verse 4, 5, and 6

David is asking the LORD to give him confidence that the LORD is indeed his salvation and that the hopes of David's enemies will never be fulfilled. David also asks the LORD to make his foes painfully aware of their own unworthiness and show them that killing David is against the LORD's plans.

Let them that seek after my soul be deceived in their hopes and become aware of their unworthiness; let them that devise my hurt fall back and find themselves unmasked.

Let them be as chaff before the wind as Your decree pushes them away.

Let their way be dark and slippery, so they stumble on the path as an angel of the LORD pursues them.

Verses 7 and 8

The standard maneuver for men of base malice was to project their own wickedness into the object of their hatred and then call it self-defense.

Let desolation come upon him unaware, and let his own snare which he secretly laid catch him; let him fall into it in desolation.

Then my soul will rejoice in the LORD; it will blissfully come into bloom in His salvation.

Verses 9 and 10

And my soul shall rejoice in the LORD; It shall exult in His salvation.

All my bones will say, "LORD, who is like You, who delivers the afflicted from him who is too strong for him, and the afflicted and the needy from him who robs him?"

Verses 11 and 12

David describes the evil plans that his enemies have employed against him.

For they rise up as witnesses of violence, they call me to account for things of which I know nothing.

They repay me evil for good; they commit the crime of kidnapping upon my soul.

Verses 13 and 14

David mourned and fasted when his enemies were ill so that they might recover.

But as for me, even when they were sick, I mourned for them; I fasted, and as for my prayer at such times, may it return into my own bosom.

As if it had been my friend or my own brother, I went about; I bowed down sorrowfully as one mourns for his own mother.

Verse 15, 16, and 17

David said that even before he fell to the ground because he stumbled, his enemies were already rejoicing together.

But at my stumbling, they rejoiced and gathered themselves together; The smiters whom I did not know gathered together against me, they slandered me without ceasing.

Like godless jesters at a feast, they gnashed at me with their teeth.

Lord, how long will You look on? Rescue my soul from their ravages, my only *life* from the lions.

Verse 18 and 19

David said that whatever he experienced of the LORD's rule and presence on earth as shown by the fate of men, he would use it to spread the recognition and homage of the LORD with all peoples.

For I am to acknowledge You to the world; I am to proclaim You among the mighty people in praise of your mighty acts.

Let them not rejoice over me, those who are my enemies for an untrue cause; let them not look daggers who hate me without cause.

Verse 20

David claimed that his enemies stood up for the cause of the people's common welfare. They were not doing that; thus, they shamed themselves with this pretense.

For they try to fool the people with peace talks, and their deceitful speech concerning the critical moments of the land.

Verse 21

וַיִּרְתְּבוּ (yayar'cheevu) – means "and to be made wide" in the possessive form. This word occurs with an exclamation of malicious joy at another's misfortune. It is similar to an "aha!" moment.

While they opened their mouths wide against me, they say, Brother, O brother, ten our sees saw it at last.

Verse 22 and 23

You have seen it, O LORD, do not keep silent; O Lord, do not be far from me.

Stir up Yourself, and awake to my right and to my cause, my God and my Lord.

Verses 24, 25, 26, and 27

David does not appeal to the LORD for justice in general. He stays on the mission that the LORD had given to him. That mission was to become the King of Israel and prepare for the Temple's building at Jerusalem.

According to Your righteousness, judge me, O LORD my God, and do not let them rejoice over me.

Do not let them say in their heart, "Aha, our desire!" Do not let them say, "We have swallowed him up!"

Let those be ashamed and humiliated altogether who rejoice at my distress; Let those be clothed with shame and dishonor who magnify themselves over me.

**Let them shout for joy and rejoice, who favor my vindication;
And let them say continually, "The LORD be magnified, who delights in the prosperity of His servant.**

Verse 28

But my tongue shall meditate upon the proclamation of Your righteousness, and upon the praise of Your might acts all day long.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

By David. Strive, O LORD, with those that contend against me; fight against them that fight against me because of who I am.

Take hold of the shield and spiked shield and rise up to my help.

And draw out the spear and barrier against them who pursue me, saying to my soul that I am your salvation.

Let them that seek after my soul be deceived in their hopes and become aware of their unworthiness; let them that devise my hurt fall back and find themselves unmasked.

Let them be as chaff before the wind as Your decree pushes them away.

Let their way be dark and slippery, so they stumble on the path as an angel of the LORD pursues them.

And my soul shall rejoice in the LORD; It shall exult in His salvation.

All my bones will say, "LORD, who is like You, who delivers the afflicted from him who is too strong for him, and the afflicted and the needy from him who robs him?"

For they rise up as witnesses of violence, they call me to account for things of which I know nothing.

They repay me evil for good; they commit the crime of kidnapping upon my soul.

But as for me, even when they were sick, I mourned for them; I fasted, and as for my prayer at such times, may it return into my own bosom.

As if it had been my friend or my own brother, I went about; I bowed down sorrowfully as one mourns for his own mother.

But at my stumbling, they rejoiced and gathered themselves together; The smiters whom I did not know gathered together against me, they slandered me without ceasing.

Like godless jesters at a feast, they gnashed at me with their teeth.

Lord, how long will You look on? Rescue my soul from their ravages, my only *life* from the lions.

For I am to acknowledge You to the world; I am to proclaim You among the mighty people in praise of your mighty acts.

Let them not rejoice over me, those who are my enemies for an untrue cause; let them not look daggers who hate me without cause.

For they try to fool the people with peace talks, and their deceitful speech concerning the critical moments of the land.

While they opened their mouths wide against me, they say, Brother, O brother, ten our sees saw it at last.

You have seen it, O LORD, do not keep silent; O Lord, do not be far from me.

Stir up Yourself, and awake to my right and to my cause, my God and my Lord.

According to Your righteousness, judge me, O LORD my God, and do not let them rejoice over me.

Do not let them say in their heart, "Aha, our desire!" Do not let them say, "We have swallowed him up!"

Let those be ashamed and humiliated altogether who rejoice at my distress; Let those be clothed with shame and dishonor who magnify themselves over me.

Let them shout for joy and rejoice, who favor my vindication;

And let them say continually, "The LORD be magnified, who delights in the prosperity of His servant.

But my tongue shall meditate upon the proclamation of Your righteousness, and upon the praise of Your might acts all day long.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

